

A Study on Improving Managerial Power and Strategies in the Field of Sports

Lin Jingfu

Zhaoqing University, Guangdong, China

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Abstract: This paper focuses on the importance of management power in sports and its application in the field of sports. Sports management power refers to the management ability of those who are engaged in management in sports organizations, clubs, stadiums and other institutions. Good sports management power can help clubs and events run smoothly, improve the level of athletes and competition, and promote the development of sports in the whole society.

Keywords: sports management power, sports organizations, clubs, competitive level, sports development.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the development of society, more and more people begin to pay attention to sports activities. Through sports activities, we can strengthen the body, cultivate the sentiment, enhance the communication ability between people, and also discover the self-worth and potential. Physical activity is of great significance to both individuals and society. However, good sports management power is needed to make sports activities have better development.

Sports management power refers to the management ability of those who are engaged in sports organization and management in sports organizations, clubs, stadiums and other institutions. Good sport management power can help clubs and events run smoothly, improve athletes' level and competition, and promote the development of sport in the whole society. The study of sport management power refers to an academic research that explores the reasons for the success of sport managers and their management skills through in-depth study of their knowledge, skills and abilities. With the continuous development of national sports and the rapid rise of sports industry, the importance of sports management power is increasingly recognized and valued. The purpose of this paper is to explore the importance of sport management power and its application in the field of sports.

II. OVERVIEW

The background of the study of sports management power lies in the fact that the sports industry is experiencing a transformation from traditional-type sports to modernized sports, which requires a group of excellent sports managers to promote and lead this change. However, most of the current sports managers in China still lack systematic and professional training and education, resulting in their uneven management level and ability. In order to solve this problem, the research and application of sports management power is particularly necessary.

In addition, with the increasing commercialization of sports, more and more enterprises and institutions are involved in sports. These organizations need a group of talents who know how to manage sports to ensure their smooth operation and management, so the study of sports management power also helps to cultivate and recommend excellent sports management talents.

Explanation of the concept of sport management power:

Sports management ability refers to the ability to use management theories, skills and methods, as well as sports professional knowledge and qualities, to coordinate and lead a team to accomplish various sports management tasks in the field of sports. Sports management ability mainly includes the ability and quality of marketing, event organization, human resources, financial management, brand building, public relations, strategic planning and so on. At the same time, sports management force also needs to have the ability of cross-border cooperation and innovation, so that it can flexibly adapt to changes and

challenges in the face of the increasingly commercialized, digitalized and globalized sports industry, and make positive contributions to the development of the sports industry.

Objectives of the study of sport management power:

1. to reveal the key factors of success in sports management: one of the objectives of research on sports management power is to explore in depth the reasons and key factors of success of sports managers, so as to provide reference and reference for sports managers;
2. to improve the effectiveness of sports management: through the study of sports management power, more scientific and precise management strategies and methods can be designed to improve the effectiveness and level of sports management.
3. to promote the development of sports industry: the study of sports management power can also promote the development and expansion of sports industry, and provide better management services and guidance for related enterprises and organizations;
4. to promote the development of national sports: the study of sports management force can help optimize the national sports management system and policies, and promote the sustainable development of national fitness and national sports.

Cultivate excellent talents: through the study of sports management force, more sports management talents with excellent management ability and quality can be cultivated, contributing to the development of the industry and social progress.

III. THE SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDYING SPORTS MANAGEMENT FORCE

1. Improve the quality of sports managers: through the study of sports management force, it can improve the quality and ability of sports managers and enhance their professional knowledge and practical ability in sports management.
2. Promote the development of sports: the study of sports management force can help managers better grasp the work of athlete training, competition organization and other aspects, so as to promote the healthy development of sports.
3. Improve the sports management mode: through the study of sports management force, the deficiencies in the current sports management mode can be found, and suggestions for improvement and optimization can be put forward to enhance the level and efficiency of sports management.
4. Promote international exchanges: Research on sport management power can promote international academic exchanges, experience sharing and cooperation, and enhance China's international influence and competitiveness.
5. Cultivate talents: Research on sport management power can help educational institutions better cultivate talents with sport management ability, and promote the smooth implementation of national fitness and national sport strategy.

IV. METHODS OF STUDYING SPORT MANAGEMENT POWER

1. questionnaire survey method: by preparing a questionnaire for sport managers, we collect their evaluation and suggestions on their own management ability, and analyze and compare the data according to the results of the questionnaire.
2. case study method: through in-depth research on the cases of successful sports management organizations or individuals, to explore the reasons for their success and management skills, and to provide reference and lessons for others.
3. Interview method: Conduct in-depth interviews with experts, coaches, athletes and administrators with rich experience in sports management to obtain their views and suggestions on sports management.
4. Field Observation Method: To understand the management style and operation mode of sport management organizations through field observation of their daily operation, and to make suggestions and recommendations for improvement based on the observation results.

V. IMPORTANCE OF SPORT MANAGEMENT POWER

Sport is a comprehensive activity that combines competition, recreation and health experience, and plays an irreplaceable role in promoting the overall development of individuals and society. Good sports management power is the foundation and guarantee to ensure the normal and orderly development of these activities. Specifically, good sports management has the following importance.

(i) Guarantee of financial security

Modern sports competitions require a large amount of capital investment, such as venue rental fees, equipment purchase costs, staff wages and so on. At the same time, competitive sports also need funds for athletes' daily training and competition support. In these issues, sports administrators often need to take various ways to effectively guarantee the security of funds, in order to better provide athletes with the corresponding conditions.

(ii) Improving organizational efficiency

Excellent sports administrators can make organizational efficiency improve. They can allocate human resources in a reasonable way, arrange athletes' training programs and make perfect competition rules. In the process of organization, managers also need to consider many factors, such as sponsors, media, government and so on, as well as the problem of coordinating the conflicting interests of all parties. Only a good organization can make sports activities richer and more meaningful.

(iii) Enhancement of the level of competition

Good sports management power not only needs to do a good job of managing athletes, but also needs to strengthen the management of the whole club. Sports managers can help clubs establish a scientific training system and enhance the competitive level. In addition, morality and ethics is also a crucial part in sports activities, and the attitudes and behaviors of sports managers can influence the formation and cognition of athletes and their families on the concept of sports ethics. Therefore, good sports administrators should always maintain high moral character and ethical standards.

VI. APPLICATION OF SPORT MANAGEMENT POWER IN THE FIELD OF SPORTS

Good sport management power is one of the keys to the success of athletes. There are various aspects of sport management power beyond funding, organizational efficiency and athleticism as mentioned above. This chapter will focus on the application of sport management power in the field of sport.

(i) Selection, recruitment and development of managers

Good sports managers can improve the efficiency of club operation and competitive level. In order to have good sport management power, clubs often make efforts in the selection, recruitment and training of sport managers. Firstly, they should make sure that the managers have high moral character; secondly, they should have professional basic knowledge, thinking ability, coordinating ability, communication ability and so on. At the same time, the club can also provide the necessary training opportunities for the managers to help them master the relevant knowledge of sports management more comprehensively.

(ii) Organize the planning and implementation of events

Good sports management requires managers to have a wide range of knowledge and skills, especially in the planning and implementation of organizing events. Issues to be considered before organizing sports competitions include venue rental, equipment purchase, staff and so on; while during the competitions, safety and security and process security are needed. Excellent sports managers can provide athletes with the best competition conditions and minimize all kinds of unnecessary interferences and disturbances.

(iii) Relationship between managers and athletes

In competitive sports, the relationship between managers and athletes is particularly important. If the managers can't deal with the relationship with athletes correctly, it will easily lead to some problems. Through the establishment of good two-way communication channels, managers can better understand the situation of athletes, make appropriate training programs, adjust the development direction of athletes, and help them achieve more excellent results.

VII. Strategies to improve sports management power

(i) Setting clear goals and plans: Sports managers should set clear goals and plans in order to achieve good management in sports teams or sports organizations. This includes identifying action objectives, resource allocation and timelines.

(ii) Establishing a team culture: Establishing a positive team culture is the key to improving sport management. The sport organization should establish a positive working atmosphere that encourages cooperation and synergy among its members, as well as a desire to work together to achieve team goals.

(iii). Promote skills training and development: sport managers should provide ongoing training and development opportunities to help staff further develop their skills and knowledge. This can be done through participation in seminars, professional courses and training programs.

(iv). Establish transparent communication mechanisms: it is very important to establish transparent communication mechanisms, especially in the sports management team. Managers should keep an open mind and listen to the opinions and ideas of their employees and communicate the information to all members of the team.

(v). Adoption of modern technology and tools: Current technology and tools can greatly enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of sport management. Sports organizations should invest in appropriate resources and adopt modern technologies and tools to better monitor, manage, and analyze data from sports teams or organizations.

(vi). Encouragement of Innovation and Continuous Improvement: innovation and improvement are important factors in improving the power of sport management. Managers should encourage their staff to come up with new ideas and innovations while continuously seeking opportunities and ways to improve.

VII. CONCLUSION

Sport management power is an essential part of modern sport activities. Through the discussion of sport management power in this paper, it can be seen that excellent sport managers need to have various qualities, including moral character, organizational ability, coordination ability and so on. Only by knowing how to utilize these qualities and management techniques can they help clubs and tournaments run smoothly, improve the level of athletes and competition, and promote the development of sports in the whole society.

In short, good sports management power must become an important element of club management. Clubs can prioritize the recruitment of high-quality managers and provide them with the necessary training opportunities. In practice, sports managers also need to focus on professional conduct and respect the ethical norms of competitive sports in order to establish a good reputation and word-of-mouth, attract more sponsors and supporters, and promote Chinese sports to a more brilliant tomorrow.

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